

Project

On

**“IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING ON
CONSUMER BEHAVIOR”**

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DECLARATION

We the undersigned solemnly declare that the report of the project work entitled “Impact of Social Media Marketing on Consumer Behavior”, is based on our own work carried out under the supervision of Dr. Sameera Raees.

We assert that the statements made and conclusions drawn are an outcome of the project work. We further declare that to the best of my knowledge and belief that the project is not a copy or an adaptation/ improvisation of the existing project. Due mention has been made of various work which has been referred to in this study and required permissions has been taken for the same.

The image shows two handwritten signatures in blue ink. The first signature is 'Utkarsh Navandar' and the second is 'Shubhangi Jain'. Both are written in a cursive style.

Signature of the Student (s)

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CERTIFICATE BY FACULTY SUPERVISOR

This to certify that the report of the project submitted is the outcome of the experiential project work entitled Impact of Social Media Marketing on Consumer Behavior carried out by Utkarsh Navandar and Shubhangi Jain bearing Roll No 3289 and 3286 of Batch under my guidance and supervision for the fulfillment of the Course- Project II.

To the best of the my knowledge the report

- a. Embodies the work of the candidate him/herself,
- b. Has duly been completed,
- c. Is up to the desired standard for the purpose of which it is submitted.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

One of the strategies that fall under the umbrella of "Digital Marketing" is "Social Media Marketing." It is a marketing strategy in which social media channels are utilised by marketers in order to engage with consumers, promote a brand and its associated products, and increase brand awareness.

The buying behaviour of consumers takes into account all of the aspects that influence the decision making process, including the consumer's attitude, preference, and the appeal of the brand, among other things.

The use of social media in marketing has a beneficial effect on the purchasing behaviours of end users. The research provides substantial data to establish that the majority of consumers are persuaded, attracted, and actually make purchases as a result of social media marketing.

The most important aspects of this research are the respondent's income, age, gender, and profession. The results of this study include information regarding the occupation, age group, and income level of individuals who are most likely to be affected by social media marketing.

In nearby future, Social Media Marketing is going to displace television as the medium that has the greatest influence on consumers. Also it not only does have an effect on the customer, but it also has a beneficial effect on the brand itself.

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INTRODUCTION

Today in this technological driven & fast paced world, everything is going digital. Since the internet is now available to an increasing number of people and has even begun to penetrate the market in rural areas, it has made it possible for businesses and their customers to communicate with one another in new ways. The usage of social media platforms is the primary method, however there are many more ways to accomplish this connection-making task. Not only do individuals utilise social media to communicate with their close friends and family members, but also businesses use it to forge a more personal relationship with their customers. When traditional marketing platforms such as television, radio, and print were the only options accessible a few years ago, people were unable to identify the brand that was linked with them. Because each of these mediums was designed with the mass market in mind, there was little room for customisation. However, due to the intimate relationship that can be formed with customers through the use of social media, this issue may often be mitigated. Businesses are increasingly turning to social media marketing (SMM). The term "social media marketing" refers to the practise of utilising various social media platforms in order to cultivate relationships with one's target consumers for the purpose of increasing website traffic, sales, and brand awareness. It includes publishing high-quality material on the social media accounts and pages of an organisation, paying attention to your followers and including them in the decision-making process, assessing your results, and placing adverts on these platforms. Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, LinkedIn, Pinterest, YouTube, Snapchat, and Whatsapp are the social media sites that are now receiving the most attention and usage (emerging fast). When it comes to buying behaviour or making a purchase decision, there are a lot of different things that might influence consumers or customers. When referring to a customer's actions in the market when purchasing a product, consumer buying behaviour refers to the accumulation of all of the customer's attitudes, preferences, intents, and decisions regarding that customer's behaviour (both goods and services). One of the most important factors that has a significant impact on customer behaviour is advertising and marketing in general. With the proliferation of the internet and various social media platforms, social media marketing has become increasingly popular. Therefore, the question that arises is whether or not social media marketing has an effect on the purchasing behaviour of consumers. If the answer is yes, then how significant is the impact, and should businesses keep using (existing) or start using (new) this particular marketing strategy? 2 This question served as the impetus for conducting the research that was presented here. The purpose of this

study is to investigate the influence that social media marketing has on the purchasing decisions of consumers. The purpose of the study is not only to determine the impact, but also to collect data on the social media platforms that are the most widely used, the various types of individuals who are affected, and the influence that social media marketing has on the organisation or brand. Primary research was selected as the method of choice for carrying out this study as a technique to obtain the necessary data for subsequent analysis. The fact that this information was gathered directly from the source eliminates any possibility of it being duplicated in any way. The research was carried out by means of the administration of a survey. The questionnaire included a wide variety of questions, ranging from demographic information to open-ended inquiries to questions about the respondents' perspectives. The data that was received through the responses were then processed and analysed so that useful insights could be obtained. Several distinct statistical tools in addition to a variety of statistical procedures were utilised in the computing process. Following the computation, the results were interpreted in a manner that enabled them to provide responses to the questions that were posed. The interpretations are supported with the assistance of some predetermined standards for the various methods that were utilised. The result at the end lives up to expectations. However, the study does have certain limitations. It's possible that this contributes to a mistake in the findings' accuracy. At the same time, it paves the way for a great deal of new research in the years to come. Whatsapp is a social media platform that is rapidly accumulating a large user base and a significant amount of popularity, particularly in India. Because of this, there is now a new platform available that can be utilised for social media marketing. A great number of well-known companies have already set up their own Whatsapp accounts and begun utilising the platform for marketing purpose. In today's world of social media, using hashtags is one of the most efficient ways to get your content noticed. It is utilised on social media platforms such as Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, Instagram, and even YouTube. On other platforms, however, this information is already public and can be utilised to construct campaigns; on YouTube, the goal is to make your video easily accessible for searches that are connected to it. It is possible for the hashtags to be campaign- or product-specific, or even the tagline of the brand itself. It is possible to utilise as hashtags even the names of celebrities who are supporting goods or regions where the campaign is shot or catering to.

Problem Statement

At the present time, one of the most popular marketing strategies is known as Social Media Marketing. The internet and platforms that are based on it are seeing explosive growth as a result of the development of new technology. The rise of social media is also contributing to this trend. There are still a great number of organisations that have not yet made the transition to social media marketing, despite the fact that many significant corporations are now using it." Facebook is the social media network that is used the most by marketers, according to a survey published by Social Media Examiner (72 %). The percentage of businesses using Instagram ads increased from 31 % in 2018 to 38 % in 2019(Post Covid more & more business have shifter to online mode thus increasing the rate rapidly). When compared to their B2B counterparts, B2C marketers are far more likely to employ social media advertising platforms such as Facebook (76 % B2C vs. 65% B2B) and Instagram (43% B2C vs. 30% B2B). B2B marketers are employing more LinkedIn ads (24 % B2B vs. 9% B2C). Better engagement is the number one goal for marking teams, followed by finding the most effective strategies to use and expanding their organic reach."

Despite the fact that the data presented above offers some insightful revelations, there are still certain questions that remain unresolved. In order to find answers to these issues, the research will concentrate on investigating the degree of influence that social media marketing has on the purchasing behaviours of customers in conjunction with a variety of other crucial characteristics. With the help of information obtained from consumers' participation in social media activities, numerous brands have been successful in determining the buying patterns of their customers. The purpose of the study is to collect evidence in support of social media marketing so that businesses that have not yet adopted this marketing strategy or those that have adopted it but are not using it in a full-fledged manner can use this research as a supporting reference for using social media marketing. The study will try to gather evidence in support of social media marketing.

Objectives of Study

- To know about impact of social media marketing on the basis of age group, profession and income.
- To know about the influence of social media marketing on purchase decision.
- To know the effect of social media marketing on the brand with regards to Trust, Brand Image, Repeat Purchase, Brand Loyalty.

Scope of Study

- Different aspects of social media marketing
- Consumer buying behavior
- Comparison of Social Media Marketing with traditional medium like TV, Print, Radio
- Social Media and its influence capability on consumers
- Social Media Platforms used by customers and marketers
- Social Media and its impact on the brand.

LITERATURE REVIEW

As a result of the increased variety and volume of information that is available over the internet, consumers are now in a position to make better judgments regarding their usage (Aksoy and Cooil, 2006). In addition, as a result of the reduction in the cost of conducting searches, new avenues for the investigation of potential pieces of evidence have become accessible (Jepsen 2007). Content and opinions provided by users frequently have an impact on the results of search engines (Smith, 2009). The influence of the Internet shifts during the many stages of decision-making. The impact of the internet has grown across all stages of decision making as a result of early developments in social media, online decision aids, and recommender systems (Karimi, 2013). People utilise social media to find information when they have the time to do so (Mangold and Faulds, 2009), such as when they are making a purchase or learning about new products or businesses (Powers et al., 2012). The utilisation of social media has resulted in the development of a cooperative environment in which customers can connect with other entities that share their preferences regarding a particular product or brand in order to engage in a never-ending cycle of exchanging views, observing progress, and requesting opinions and rankings on a vast array of products (including both goods and services) and activities (Ashman et al., 2015). According to Zhou et al. (2013) and Zhang et al. (2013), the perceived informativeness and persuasiveness of online product evaluations, as well as the perceived number of reviews, positively influence consumers' purchase intentions. In addition, Zhou et al. (2013) found that consumers' purchase intentions are positively influenced by the perceived number of reviews (2014). The information obtained through PR and marketing is less reliable than that obtained through social networking. Constantinides believes that there is a lack of faith in the mainstream media (2014). As a result, consumers are turning away from traditional media (Mangold and Faulds, 2009)" The use of social media makes it simpler for businesses to collect feedback from customers and to conduct research in real time. It is possible to achieve this goal by mandating that workers take an active part in online discussions and that they also pay attention to and read what members of the general public have to say in various online communities, forums, and blogs (Constantinides, 2014). Customers were able to feel more at ease while using social media during the initial phases of information search and alternative evaluation; however, the use of social media did not significantly contribute to the growth of customer satisfaction during the stages of making a purchase decision or evaluating the product after it had been purchased (D. Voramontri and L. Klieb, 2018). 6

The interaction between social media and the decision-making process of consumers demonstrates that social media influences customers' attitudes toward advertising and companies, as well as their intents to make purchases. [C]onsumers' decision-making processes are influenced by social media. It is unlikely that it will have a direct impact on the choices made by customers, but it may have a moderating effect (Taining, 2012). "Organizations have the ability to establish tactics that can affect the purchasing decisions of customers by using social media. When it comes to making a choice about what to buy, a customer's preference can be swayed by the positive reputation of the company or product in question. Word-of-mouth publicity and referrals made through social media by friends and family members of customers have an impact on the image of the company as well as the decisions that customers make regarding their purchases. In addition, customers' views of businesses and their desire to make purchases are impacted by adverts that appear on social media platforms (Yang, 2012).

"The utilisation of social media marketing has significantly expanded the availability of pertinent information and the transparency of its presentation to customers. This information is not only more comprehensive, but it is also much simpler to obtain. Customers are increasingly providing content and contributing to the co-creation of value that is now taking place. The mindsets of customers are influenced by social media, which in turn increases their willingness to make purchases. (Gulzar Asma and Maqbool Misbah, 2018). The phrase "social networking sites serve as a communication route between consumers and organisations, which in turn helps in the management of customer relationship management (CRM) systems" (Evans, 2010). According to the conclusions of the study, social media marketing is an essential instrument for the promotion of businesses, products, and services. This is due to the rapidly increasing popularity of social media as well as changes in the behaviour of customers. According to the findings, social media marketing has the potential to impact customers at all stages of the purchasing decision process (Fauser et al., 2011). The use of social media presents potential for companies to become more appealing to their clientele (Chen et al. 2011b).

When social aspects are developed through the utilisation of social media, a favourable environment is produced, which in turn encourages additional entities to go online and participate in social communication (M. Nick Hajli, 2013).

According to Schivinski and Dabrowski (2016), communication through social media has a positive effect on the equity of a brand as well as the attitude that consumers have toward the business. According to the findings, a consumer's disposition toward a brand and evaluation of the brand's worth have a favourable influence on the consumer's propensity to make purchases of that brand.

In order to gain an understanding of how decisions are made, the decision-process method investigates both the events that take place before and after a purchase. "The purpose of the study should be taken into consideration before attempting to model client behaviour" (Karimi, 2013). Consumer decision-making can be defined as "consumer behaviour patterns that precede, determine, and follow the decision process for acquiring need-satisfying items, ideas, or services," as stated by Du Plessis and the other researchers that worked with him (1991). [2] The economic model, the psychological model, the Pavlovian learning model, and the sociological model are some of the consumer simulations that are the most straightforward. The decade of the 1960s came to a close with the publication of works such as Nicosia (1966), Engel et al. (1978), and Howard and Sheth (1970). (1969). There are numerous examples of "grand models" of appropriate consumer behaviour. Nicosia (1966) proposed that there are four stages in the decision-making process of a consumer: the creation of attitudes, the search for and evaluation of information, the actual purchase, and post-consumption feedback. In addition to inputs (stimuli), perceptual and learning components, outputs (customer behaviour and purchase choice), and external variables, the model that Howard and Sheth (1969) developed contains all of these elements (social, psychological and marketing factors). Information input, processing, decision phases, and decision process variables are the four parts that make up the EKB model, which Engel et al. (1990) referred to as the EBM. The process of decision-making for consumers consists of five stages: the recognition of a need, the search for information, the evaluation of various options, the purchase (or option), and the post-purchase results. The progression through each stage is influenced by a distinct set of qualities, contextual variables, and psychological processes. "Information overload" is a challenge that comes up when making decisions online. Because of the concept of limited rationality (Simon, 1960; Thaler and Mullainathan, 2008), there is a limit to the amount of data that individuals are able to digest, and it is not possible to do an

in-depth analysis of all of the available options for making a decision. This shows that people are more likely to make snap judgments rather than thoughtfully examining all of their options. (Karimi, 2013)."

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

"Google Forms, which can be based on a web link and which can be used in all internet operating systems such as Internet Explorer, Google Chrome, Firefox, and Mac OS, amongst others, were used to create a web-designed questionnaire specifically for the purpose of conducting this research. An online survey with a structured questionnaire presented in the form of a web page was used to collect primary data for the purpose of addressing both dependent and independent variables. This survey was distributed across the most popular social media platforms, including Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, WhatsApp, and LinkedIn." [6] In addition to that, the referral mechanism was utilised in order to broaden the scope of the circulation. The type of research being conducted is inductive, and quantitative methods and tools are being used in the analysis of the variables. "The primary data are gathered through the use of structured questionnaires with closed statements that are rated on a scale developed by Likert." [6] (1-5 as very frequently -never), yes/no/may be questions and some straight questions." The focus of this research is on more complicated purchases that call for extensive problem solving; these are the types of transactions that are more likely to make use of social media. The next question that was asked of the respondents was whether or not they had used social media in the process of making their decision. The questions measured the same concepts in each of the different scenarios, and the wording of the questions varied from one context to the next only very slightly." [2] The fact that the Buyer choice feature does not include any objective dimensions makes its operation tricky. It's possible to take an objective or subjective approach when evaluating the quality of a decision, according to Aksoy and Cooil (2006). [2] Subjective techniques are evaluations of the decision-maker in which the aspects that are most important to the respondent in relation to the decision are taken into consideration. The survey was constructed in such a way so that it could measure the influence of social media marketing on customer behaviour based on various parameters such as age, gender, occupation, income, and so on.

The Model

Dependent variable: Consumer Buying Behaviour (CBB)

Marketing on social media constitutes the independent variable (SMM)

The model is as follows: $CBB = f(SMM)$

Hypotheses Based On Research

On the basis of demographic characteristics, there is no influence of SMM on consumers, as stated in the H1 clause.

On the basis of demographic characteristics, there is an impact of SMM on consumers, as stated in the first hypothesis.

When it comes to making a purchasing decision, customers are not swayed by SMM, as stated in Hypothesis 2'.

During the process of making a purchase choice, consumers are influenced by social media marketing. H2:

On the basis of the many criteria, H3 asserts that SMM has no effect on the brand.

H3: Social media marketing has a favourable impact on brands based on a variety of characteristics including trust and brand image

Note

Hypothesis H': The Null Hypothesis

H: A Different Version Of The Hypothesis

Sampling Design

The individuals who utilise social media networks as a whole served as the respondents in this study, which totaled 151 people. The respondents were from all around India and Nepal; however, a small percentage of respondents were from countries other than India and Nepal,

such as Zimbabwe, Botswana, Afghanistan, and so on. These individuals who are citizens of other countries currently call India their home. The ages of the people who answered the survey range from 15 to over 40 years old. Respondents come from a variety of backgrounds, with the majority of them being students. This makes the sample more representative of the population as a whole because students are more likely to be active on social media. The requirement of providing an email address was made mandatory so that errors caused by duplicated data might be avoided. It prevents multiple responses from being sent from the same email address.

Techniques for Conducting Statistical Analysis

The following methods were utilised in the analysis of the data by utilising SPSS:

- Cross-tabulation: a method for analysing the correlation between a number of different parameters
- Correlation: to investigate the relationship between the influence of social media marketing on customer purchasing behaviour

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Q1. Gender

Figure 1 Gender Ratio

Men and women made up 92 and 59, respectively, of the 151 responders overall.

As a result, there were 60 men and 40 women among our responders, dividing them in a 60:40 ratio. The ratio clearly illustrates the disparity between male & women.

Q2. Age Group

Figure 2 Age Group of Respondents

Age ranges from 15 to over 40 years are represented among the responders. The age range of 21 to 25 years has the most respondents, followed by those between 26 and 30 and those between 15 and 20 years old.

The other age group is slightly older, starting at 31 years old.

The respondent's age indicates that the data may portray accurate results because younger people are the major social media users since the research relates to the field of social media marketing.

Q3. What is your Annual Family Income?

Figure 3 Annual Family income of respondents

Only 146 of the 151 respondents decided to answer a question regarding their yearly salary. The majority of respondents reported having a family income of at least Rs. 5 lakhs.

The goal of gathering information on respondents' incomes is to determine the association between family income and decisions made as a result of social media marketing.

Q4. What is your profession?

Figure 4 Profession of Respondents

The respondents in the survey sample represent a variety of professions. The majority of responders are students, which should not be surprising given that the majority of respondents are young adults. After students, business and corporate, respectively, are the other professions with the highest response rates. The remaining responders fall under the Other and Financial Services group. Professionals including homemakers, engineers, government employees, service providers, and photographers are included in the Other group. It's interesting that nobody checked the box for unemployment.

We can infer from the data above that users of social media come from a variety of professions. Everywhere social media is pervasive.

Q5. Which social media platform you use the most?

Figure 5 Social Media Platform Preferred by them

Using social media has become standard practise in the current technology and socially connected world.

Additionally, it is fairly evident that many people use various social media sites given the variety of social media platforms available to us.

The purpose of this question was to find out which social media network, out of several possibilities, respondents used the most. Facebook is a major player across all social media platforms, thus it seems sense, based on the data we collect, that respondents would choose Facebook as their preferred social media site. Instagram regularly monitors it. YouTube has a sizable user base as well. The remaining platforms, including LinkedIn and Twitter, don't seem to be very important.

WhatsApp is the platform that respondents have indicated as being "Other." WhatsApp is currently not a fully functional marketing tool for brands, so I did not offer it as an alternative. WhatsApp does not, however, permit advertisements, so it cannot be used as a social media market

Q6. How frequently you come across advertisement on Social Media?

Figure 6 Frequency of Advertisements on Social Media

The Likert Scale has been used here to record the responses. The actions were:

1 - Never

5- Very Frequently

The results show that the majority of people are exposed to these platforms' advertising on a regular basis. This indicates that businesses are heavily investing in "Social Media Marketing."

Q7. How influential to a purchase decision do you think social media marketing is?

Figure 7 Influence on Purchase Decision

The majority of responders confirm that social media marketing has an impact on buying choices. This also justifies the significant sums that businesses spend on social media advertising because it allows them to influence customers as they shop.

The relationship between many elements and the criteria in this question is now being examined.

- Age group-Influence Level
- Profession-Influence Level
- Income-Influence Level

Q8. In which platform do you notice more advertisements?

Figure 8 Most number of advertisements seen on Social Media

The purpose of this inquiry was to identify the social media platform that, in the opinions of the respondents, features the greatest number of adverts. It should not come as a surprise that Facebook came out on top in terms of advertisement platform, given that it is also the social media network that is utilised the most frequently all over the world. YouTube comes in at number two on the list, followed by Instagram and LinkedIn in that order. Unsurprisingly, nobody has voted for the social networking site Twitter.

Now that we have that out of the way, let's look at the relationship between the social media platform that is being used and the maximum number of adverts that are being viewed on these platforms. The following question can therefore be answered with the use of this information:

Is there a correlation between using a particular social media site and watching the highest number of advertisements on that particular platform?

Q9. Do you think social media marketing help you recognize the brand?

Figure 9 Recognition of Brand by their Social Media presence

A little over 72% of respondents concurred with the statement that social media marketing does aid in increasing brand recognition.

19% of respondents think that social media marketing might assist in recognising the brand, while the remaining 9% are adamant that social media marketing does not assist in recognising the brand.

As a result of our investigation into the connection between Profession and these criteria, we are able to answer the following questions: Which profession is most likely to agree that Social Media Marketing assists them in recognising the brand?

*It is important to note that the affirmative responses "Yes" and "Maybe" are both taken into consideration.

Q10. Do you think social media marketing is an effective marketing strategy for the organizations?

Figure 10 Effect of Social Media

The vast majority of respondents are under the impression that marketing through social media is an efficient technique that organisations should implement. This provides additional support for the justification of the expenditures that organisations make on social media marketing. An efficient method of marketing is social media marketing (SMM) since it improves brand recognition and also has a favourable influence on the choice to make a purchase.

Q11. Have you been enticed by an advertisement on social media to buy a product?

Figure 11 Influence of Advertisements

As per the figure illustrated above majority of people have been enticed to buy a product through an advertisement on social media.

67% of total respondents reacted yes to our question.

Only 16% respondents says no.

17 % says maybe.

Q12. What kind of advertisement on social media you come across the most?

Figure 12 Kind of advertisement you come across

The objective of this question is to find out which types of advertisements are most frequently seen by the respondents, which in turn may bring forth information on which types of advertisements are most frequently utilised in social media marketing.

According to the responses, the types of advertisements that are most frequently employed are referred to as "Audio-Video" and "Graphic/Image" in that respective order.

Now that we have the criteria, we will attempt to analyse them using a variety of metrics.

Type of Advertising that is Employed Primarily on Social Media Platforms

Appeal to Customers Via Social Media Marketing-Style Advertisement.

Q13. Have you ever made a purchase because of social media marketing?

Figure 13 Decision due to Social Media Marketing

The figure from response illustrates that huge section of human population made a purchase because of social media marketing & henceforth social media marketing affect the consumer behaviour.

68% of total respondents made purchase because of social media marketing.

Q14. Which of the following medium of advertisements have more impact than social media marketing?

Figure 14 Medium of Advertisement with more influence than social media

Advertisements on television continue to have the greatest impact on individuals, despite the fact that people are becoming more influenced by social media. This question was posed with the intention of identifying the types of advertising platforms that, in comparison to social media, carry a greater degree of weight.

It is possible to deduce the following:

When it comes to advertising, television continues to have the greatest impact as a medium.

A relatively tiny fraction of respondents are under the impression that print media have a greater impact than social media.

A sizeable portion of the population holds the misconception that traditional marketing channels, such as television, print, and radio, are more influential than social media marketing.

No one voted for Radio, which comes as a surprise.

Q15. Do you think that in the next 5 years Social Media Marketing would become the medium of advertisement having maximum impact?

Figure 15 Future of Social Media Marketing

The purpose of asking this question is to learn about people's perspectives on the direction that social media marketing will take in the future.

Inferences such as the following can be drawn from the chart:

The vast majority of the replies indicate that social media will evolve into the kind of advertising that has the potential to have the greatest impact during the next five years.

In general, it is possible to draw the conclusion that businesses ought to make better use of social media for marketing purposes by utilising it in a more efficient and effective manner. In addition, a sizeable number of respondents believe that social media may one day become the most important form of advertising.

Now that we have that out of the way, let's examine the connection between Profession and this criterion.

Q16. How often do you see your favorite brand advertise on these platforms?

Figure 16 Frequency of your favorite brand advertisement

We get a different image of the frequency of adverts from this question. The majority of respondents to the previous question acknowledged that they frequently view commercials on social media sites, however when the same question was posed regarding their favourite brand, the majority of respondents responded with a "3," or moderate.

From the foregoing, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- 1.Their preferred brand is not investing in SMM in comparison to other competitors.
- 2.The top brands which extensively use SMM are not their favourite brand.

FINDINGS

The study of the data provides sufficient evidence to refute all of the null hypotheses and to acknowledge the validity of all of the alternative hypotheses.

Because to social media marketing, people in younger age groups (those with less than 30 years of experience) are more likely to be influenced, attracted, and ultimately make a purchase decision.

Because of social media marketing, professionals in fields like business, student, and corporate are more likely to be influenced, intrigued, and ultimately persuaded to make a purchase.

Because people in lower income brackets are less likely to be affected and lured by social media marketing, this type of marketing is not as effective for selling expensive goods as it is for selling cheaper goods.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- The majority of respondents' preferred brands did not make considerable use of social media platforms for advertising purposes, which indicates that these businesses have room for development in this area. Because the results that we have obtained indicate that the use of social media has a favourable impact on the brand, they should increase their use of social media marketing.
- According to the findings of a survey by Social Media Examiner, Facebook has been steadily losing its market share because the majority of its users are now more interested in using Instagram. Even this study highlights the fact that, as of right now, Instagram has a user base that is practically identical to that of Twitter. Therefore, businesses need to start concentrating more of their efforts on Instagram if they want to succeed in social media marketing.
- As a result of our research, we discovered that traditional marketing methods, such as television and print advertising, are more effective for selling high-priced products than social media marketing. As a result, businesses that sell these types of products should reduce their use of social media marketing and focus more on traditional advertising methods.
- The graphic/image and audio-video types of commercials should be given greater attention because consumers view these types of advertisements the most frequently and they have a very significant influence on consumers.
- Because the usage of Social Media Marketing can have a beneficial effect on a company's brand, companies should make responsible use of this marketing strategy.
- The research provides compelling evidence that social media marketing will become the channel with the greatest influence on customers in the foreseeable future. Therefore, businesses should begin to see marketing on social media as a fundamental endeavour and begin implementing it in its entirety as soon as possible.

LIMITATIONS OF STUDY

- The research was carried out based on the responses of 151 participants, which is an extremely small sample size compared to the whole number of people who use social media throughout the world. Therefore, if we talk about those who utilize social media in general, the findings of this study could not be applicable at all.
- The number of male respondents outnumbered female respondents by a factor of 60 to 40. Because of this, the investigation of the various criteria on the basis of gender was restricted because a greater number of male participants may have influenced the actual results.
- Whatsapp being one of the most used social media platform amongst all the age group for quick conversations but since there is currently no facility for display advertisements on WhatsApp, it is not taken into consideration as a potential advertising platform.
- Twitter hasn't been taken into consideration because of the niche it serves.

CONCLUSION

The use of various social media platforms by business organisations to promote their product (both goods and services), connect with customers on a more personal level, and make sales through the use of these channels is referred to as social media marketing (SMM). SMM can also be used to connect with customers on a global scale. It's possible that traditional advertising mediums like TV and print are having more impact than social media marketing right now, but the research presented in this paper suggests that within the next five years, social media will take over as the medium with the greatest impact, replacing TV in that role. Therefore, at this point in time, it is perfectly appropriate for businesses to utilise social media marketing to the fullest extent that they are capable of. The phrase "consumer buying behaviour" refers to the aggregate of a customer's attitudes, preferences, intentions, and decisions surrounding their actions in the market when they are making a purchase of a product (both goods and services). The research reaches the additional conclusion that marketing via social media has a beneficial effect, not only on consumer purchasing behaviour but also on the brand itself. The vast majority of consumers are swayed, lured, and ultimately persuaded to make a purchase as a direct result of marketing on social media. The vast majority of people now have access to the internet, which has led to a considerable increase in the number of people using various forms of social media. Because of this, business organisations now have an opportunity to capitalise and make the most of what it has to offer. Additionally, as a result of the rapid pace at which technology innovation is occurring, social media platforms are continuously releasing new features for their user bases. These are the factors that need to be considered by the organisations before a social media marketing strategy can be developed that is effective.

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APPENDICES

The screenshot shows a Google Form titled "Figure 17 Questionnaire" displayed in a Chrome browser. The form contains two questions:

- Gender?**
 - Female
 - Male
 - Other
- Age?**
 - 15-20
 - 21-25
 - 26-30
 - 31-35
 - 36-40
 - 40+

At the bottom right of the form, there is a button labeled "Request edit access". The browser's address bar shows the URL: `docs.google.com/forms/d/159gJua9vzHfQCVZXR3S4YTIKToebINIP88S1Pvndg/viewform?edit_requested=true`. The Windows taskbar at the bottom shows the date as 13-07-2022 and the time as 19:58.

Figure 17 Questionnaire

The screenshot shows a Google Form titled "Figure 18 Questionnaire" displayed in a Chrome browser. The form contains two questions:

- Profession?**
 - Student
 - Business
 - Corporate
 - Financial Service
 - Unemployed
 - Other
- Annual Family Income?**
 - Less than 3 lakhs
 - Between 3-5 lakhs
 - Between 5- 10 lakhs
 - 10 lakhs & above

At the bottom right of the form, there is a button labeled "Request edit access". The browser's address bar shows the URL: `docs.google.com/forms/d/159gJua9vzHfQCVZXR3S4YTIKToebINIP88S1Pvndg/viewform?edit_requested=true`. The Windows taskbar at the bottom shows the date as 13-07-2022 and the time as 19:58.

Figure 18 Questionnaire

Figure 19 Questionnaire

Figure 20 Questionnaire

Figure 21 Questionnaire

Figure 22 Questionnaire

Do you think social media marketing is an effective marketing strategy for the organizations?

Yes
 No
 Maybe

Have you been enticed by an advertisement on social media to buy a product?

Yes
 No
 Maybe

What kind of advertisement on social media you come across the most?

Text
 Audio
 Graphic/Image

[Request edit access](#)

Figure 23 Questionnaire

Which of the following medium of advertisements have more impact than social media marketing?

TV
 Radio
 Print
 All of the above

Do you think that in the next 5 years Social Media Marketing would become the medium of advertisement having maximum impact?

Yes
 No
 Maybe

[Submit](#) [Clear form](#)

[Request edit access](#)

Figure 24 Questionnaire

PLAGIARISM REPORT

Match Overview ×

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